

STYLISTIC ANALYSIS OF APHORISMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19367502>

Keywords: *stylistics, stylistic device, metaphor, antithesis, hyperbole, alliteration.*

We use many language units in our speech. Each of them has its own role and serves to convey speech in a clear, concise manner. In particular, aphorisms in our language have become a part of our daily life. Aphorisms can be found not only in daily life, but also in various articles, TV shows, literary works and many advertisements.

Aphorisms can contain various stylistic devices. For example: antithesis, metaphor, hyperbole, alliteration, etc. Each of them is important in aphorisms. Metaphor describes objects in sentences by comparing them to each other, antithesis describes sentences through contrasts, hyperbole exaggerates them and alliteration describes them with melody.

"The term metaphor is defined as the transference of a name belonging to one object, phenomenon, action, or feature to another." [Sh.Safarov, 2023] The emergence of metaphorical transfer is based on a certain similarity between the compared are the most common types of stylistic devices in aphorisms. Compared to other types of stylistic devices, they are more active in aphorisms, and in most cases they can be found as part of in one aphorism structure.

Comfort and prosperity have never enriched the world as much as adversity has. [R.Agarwall, 2008]

B.Graham

"Comfort/prosperity" and "adversity" are contradictory words. "Enriched the world" metaphor shows the enriching power of suffering on humanity.

Ketgan molga achinma, unga ozroq o'kingil. M.Qoshg'ariy [E.Sultonov, 2019]

In this Uzbek aphorism the word "mol" also refers to things, objects, and opportunities, while the words "achinma" and o'kingil" words express the opposite meaning.

In addition, hyperbole is also found in aphorisms, and its function in aphorisms can be said to be a stylistic device that strengthens the idea, has an emotional impact on the reader, and helps the idea be remembered figuratively. The word hyperbole is considered different explanations by scholars. According to R.Carston, "hyperbole is a trope that involves deliberate overstatement of a certain degree [Carston.R. 2015] Harres added that the element of hyperbole is exaggeration".

We all fly. Once you leave the ground, you fly. Some people fly longer than others. M.Jordan [R.Agarwall, 2008]

This aphorism, which expresses the idea that some people fly longer than others, refers to the non-human quality of "flying". In fact, M.Jordan meant by the word "fly" how long a person will live before leaving this world.

Filning dumi bo'lguncha chumolining boshi bo'l. A.Temur [A.Raimov, N.Raimova. 2019]

Our great ancestor A.Temur due to his great military leadership, expressed many thoughts in his aphorisms about the qualities of national courage, protecting the homeland, not bowing down to others, and being respectful towards people around him. The idea is expressed that live not by someone else's opinion, but by your own destiny, by your own opinion, even if it is

of little importance, and have your own views and your own independence, no matter who compliments you.

Alliteration can also be recognized as one of the most frequently used active stylistic devices in aphorisms. Alliteration is not only the repetition of consonants and vowels at the beginning of a sentence, but also the harmony of letters between sentences, providing melodiousness. In English language alliteration can be classified as 12 types by H.Landis, but in Uzbek language it can be classified as vertical and horizontal types by scholars A.Berdiyev, A.Haydarov and M.Yuldoshev.

Wisdom waits; wit won't. O.Uvayld [V.H Auden, L.Kronenberger,1962]

A clear example of alliteration in these lines are called sibilant alliteration, such as *Wisdom waits, but reason does not*, can be seen in the sequential use of the letter "w". This aphorism expresses the states of patience and haste in man. Its main idea is that wisdom takes a long time, while haste involves thinking and living life on the basis of speed.

O world invisible, we view thee :

O world intangible, we touch thee,

O world unknowable, we know thee,

Inapprehensible, we clutch thee. F.Tomson [R.Agarwall, 2008]

It is clear from these examples that first example of alliteration is given as a horizontal alliteration, the second type alliteration is given a vertical.

Qanoat birla qorin to'yg'uzursiz;

Qanoat bo'lmasa, ko'p och qolursiz.

Qanoatsiz kishi bag'rini dog'lar;

Qanoatlik kishi og'zini yog'lar. A.Avloniy [A.Ochildiyev, 2023]

In this aphorism, A. Avloni expresses his opinion about what a satisfied and dissatisfied person is like, and the use of the word "qanoat" at the beginning of sentences is an example of vertical alliteration. When alliteration is used in aphorisms, it is not only the beginning of each word that is the same consonant, but also the words quoted at the beginning of each line, expressed in a poetic form, when the first letter of the first word begins with the same consonant, it also demonstrates alliteration.

Table. 1 The function of stylistic devices in aphorisms

Stylistic device	Main function	Result
Antithesis	to create contradiction among sentences	to show clear views
Metaphor	figurative meaning	to provide imagination
Hyperbole	exaggeration	to increase efficiently
Alliteration	repetition of sound	to give melody

In conclusion, it should be said that these stylistic devices serve to increase the effectiveness of aphorisms, to convey ideas concisely and to ensure that the content is deep and impressive.

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